

Titrimetric Determination of Thiols and Thioureas with Masson and Race Reagent

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Simple, accurate and direct titrimetric methods for the determination of aliphatic as well as aromatic thiols and alkyl and aryl derivatives of thiourea, have been described. The end point is signalled visually using starch as indicator and potentiometrically by a large potential jump. The procedures are accurate to $\pm 0.3\%$ with the precision $\pm 0.4\%$.

THE ubiquitous sulphhydryl radical has been the subject of much analytical researches¹⁻¹⁰. The classical method using iodine, has been modified favourably for the determination of cysteine¹¹. In the course of our studies on the determination of thiols, consideration was given to the possible use of Masson and Race reagent. The reagent has been found to oxidise thiols quantitatively to their corresponding disulphides in dilute acetic acid.

Thioureas^{12,13} are biologically, commercially and medicinally important compounds. Several approaches for their assay have been reviewed¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Masson and Race reagent is employed for the quantitative oxidation of thiourea and its *N*-substituted-alkyl and -aryl derivatives in sulphuric acid medium; corresponding formamidine disulphides are the reaction products.

Preisler and Barger¹⁸ found oxidation reduction potential of thiourea formamidine disulphide system to be 0.420 V in 0.05 to 1 N HCl. They stated that this system was analogous to the thiol-disulphide system ($2\text{RSH} \rightarrow \text{R}-\text{S}-\text{S}-\text{R} + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}$).

Experimental

Masson and Race reagent¹⁹ solution (0.05 N) was prepared by adding iodine (0.635 g) and iodine pentoxide (1.25 g) to concentrated sulphuric acid (100 ml). After stirring, the mixture was diluted to 500 ml and cooled well. It was finally made upto 1 dm² and standardised iodometrically. As a check of the present procedures, thioureas were determined by oxidation with hypiodite, bromine and iodine, and mercaptans with iodine and iodine monochloride.

Most of the mercaptans were gift from Evans Chemitics, New York.

Procedure for thioureas: An aliquot of the sample dissolved in water containing thiourea function (~ 0.2 mmol) was pipetted into a 250 ml flask. Enough sulphuric or hydrochloric acid was added to keep the concentration of acid to 1 N when alkylthioureas were determined. Each aryl derivative was dissolved in 10-15 ml sulphuric acid (18 N) and at the time of titration water was added to bring the concentration of acid to ~ 3.5 N. The sample solutions were cooled to room temperature and titrated with 0.05 N solutions of Masson and Race reagent after adding starch solution (1 ml, 1%). At the end-point a blue colour was formed.

Potentiometric titrations were performed by taking the sample in the range as above in a 150 ml beaker keeping other conditions same. A platinum-calomel electrode pair was used. The end-point was shown by a large potential jump.

Procedure for mercaptans: A sample containing thiol (0.1-1.0 mmol) was weighed in a 150 ml flask and dissolved in water (30 ml) or glacial acetic acid (5-10 ml) but at the time of titration sufficient water was added to bring acid concentration to about 30%. Starch solution (1 ml, 1%) was added and the solution was titrated with 0.05 N Masson and Race reagent to blue colour.

In potentiometric titrations, the procedure followed was the same as described above for thioureas.

The results for the determination of thiols are summarised in Table 1. The results obtained by potentiometric titration agreed with the visual-indicator results within $\pm 0.3\%$. To check the accuracy of the proposed procedure, thiols were determined by independent methods and the purity thus estimated agreed within analytical precision with those obtained by the reagent under investigation. Thiocarbonyl compounds, sulphide and sulphocyanide ions interfere.

Mercaptosuccinic acid, *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid, 3-mercaptopropionic acid and cysteine give erron-

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THIOLS WITH MASSON AND RACE REAGENT

Compd.	Purity, %		
	Masson and Race*		Comparison method
	Visual*	Potentiometry	
Ethanthiol	97.9	98.0	98.1 ^a Iodimetry
Glutathione	97.9	97.6	97.8 ^b Iodimetry
4-Chlorobenzene thiol	96.2	95.9	96.1 ^c Pb ²⁺ titration
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	96.7	96.2	96.6 ^d ICl titration
4-Toluene thiol	98.2	98.3	98.5 ^e Co ²⁺ titration
2-Diethylaminoethane thiol	98.1	98.5	98.2 ^f Chloramine-T
2-Mercaptoethanol	90.4	90.0	99.3 ^g Cu ²⁺ titration
Mercaptoacetic acid	80.5	80.5	80.3 ^h HIO ₃ titration
Thiobenzoic acid	94.9	95.2	95.0 ^b Alkalimetry
1-Butane thiol	90.7	90.4	90.6 ^g o-DIB titration
2-Mercaptoethylammonium chloride	97.6	97.2	97.5 ⁱ o-Iodosobenzoate
2-Naphthalene thiol	98.9	99.4	99.1 ^b Alkalimetry
1-Glycerol thiol	88.1	88.0	88.2 ^j Monochloramine

* Average of 10 determination.

^aJ. W. Kimball, R. L. Kramer and E. E. Reid, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1199. ^bJ. W. Patterson and A. Lazarow in "Methods of Biochemical Analysis", ed. D. Glick, Interscience, New York, 1961, Vol. II, p. 267. ^cL. Suehomelova and J. Zyka, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, 5, 57. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 10. ^fRef. 6. ^gRef. 8. ^hJ. S. Fritz and N. M. Lisicki, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 589. ⁱH. V. Malmstadt and D. A. Vassallo, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 862. ^jRef. 7.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THIOUREAS WITH MASSON AND RACE REAGENT

	Purity, %		
	Masson and Race*		Comparison method
	Visual	Potentiometric	
Thiourea	99.7	99.8	99.9 ^a NaCl
Allylthiourea	98.2	98.1	98.5 ^a ICl
Methylthiourea	99.3	99.0	99.5 Ce ²⁺
Amylthiourea	98.8	98.7	99.0 ^a ICl
Butylthiourea	97.7	97.8	97.3 ^a ICl
Phenylthiourea	96.4	96.3	96.6 ^b o-Diacetoxyiodobenzoate
p-Tolylthiourea	97.3	97.5	97.5 ^c Chloramine-T

*Average of 10 determinations.

^aRef. 15. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 15.

euos results. An examination of these thiols, reveals that they have a common structural feature, a carboxyl group on a carbon atom β to the sulphur atom. This conformation causes an intramolecular displacement reaction forming a five membered cyclic intermediate. Instead of forming disulphide, this intermediate alternatively undergoes further oxidation to sulphonic acid and higher oxidation states. Thiols, like 2-mercaptoacetic acid, 2-mercaptoethanol, 2-mercaptoethylamine, 2-mercaptoethylammonium chloride, 2-mercaptoethanol, 2-mercaptoacetic acid and *m*- and *p*-mercaptobenzoic acids without a β -carboxyl group are not susceptible for over-oxidation and hence give a clean stoichiometry.

Results for thiourea derivatives are summarised in Table 2. Purity determined by the proposed method is comparable with the reported methods.

The direct method is simple, accurate and quick.

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